

Batch Analysis Report

Run Date: 12/5/23 11:04 AM

Experiment: 20231205_Ilyas zfish sc GFP 100u...

User ID: Ilyas

Statistics Output: N/A

Worksheet PDF Output: D:\BDEExport\Experiment\AG Becker\Ilyas_FACS\batch_analyses\20231205_Ilyas zfish sc GFP 100um_scRNA-seq_sema4ab-Batch_Analysis_05122023110401.pdf

spinal cord

Tube	Status	Run Time
control submitted	OK	12/5/23 11:04 AM
control postsort	OK	12/5/23 11:04 AM
sema4ab submitted	OK	12/5/23 11:05 AM
sema4ab sort	OK	12/5/23 11:05 AM
sema4ab postsort	OK	12/5/23 11:05 AM

BD FACSDiva 9.0.1

Tube: control submitted

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	311,075	####	100.0
cells	187,445	60.3	60.3
FSC Singlets	143,765	76.7	46.2
viable PI-	137,337	95.5	44.1
autofluo AF	4,093	3.0	1.3
GFP total	2	0.0	0.0
negative	132,910	96.8	42.7
GFP strong	0	0.0	0.0
GFP weak	2	0.0	0.0
PI+	1,400	1.0	0.5
viable PI-	240,390	77.3	77.3
P1	72,287	23.2	23.2

BD FACSDiva 9.0.1

Tube: control postsort

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	20,891	####	100.0
cells	5,907	28.3	28.3
FSC Singlets	5,623	95.2	26.9
viable PI-	2,966	52.7	14.2
autofluo AF	77	2.6	0.4
GFP total	0	0.0	0.0
negative	2,878	97.0	13.8
GFP strong	0	0.0	0.0
GFP weak	0	0.0	0.0
PI+	1,977	35.2	9.5
viable PI-	5,537	26.5	26.5
P1	13,421	64.2	64.2

BD FACSDiva 9.0.1

Tube: sema4ab submitted

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	329,500	####	100.0
cells	188,381	57.2	57.2
FSC Singlets	142,994	75.9	43.4
viable PI-	135,212	94.6	41.0
autofluo AF	5,125	3.8	1.6
GFP total	1	0.0	0.0
negative	129,802	96.0	39.4
GFP strong	0	0.0	0.0
GFP weak	1	0.0	0.0
PI+	2,023	1.4	0.6
viable PI-	251,376	76.3	76.3
P1	82,563	25.1	25.1

BD FACSDiva 9.0.1

Tube: sema4ab sort

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	72,650	####	100.0
cells	41,430	57.0	57.0
FSC Singlets	32,136	77.6	44.2
viable PI-	30,188	93.9	41.6
autofluo AF	1,110	3.7	1.5
GFP total	0	0.0	0.0
negative	29,019	96.1	39.9
GFP strong	0	0.0	0.0
GFP weak	0	0.0	0.0
PI+	653	2.0	0.9
viable PI-	55,899	76.9	76.9
P1	18,186	25.0	25.0

BD FACSDiva 9.0.1

Tube: sema4ab postsort

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	17,077	####	100.0
cells	9,262	54.2	54.2
FSC Singlets	9,030	97.5	52.9
viable PI-	7,248	80.3	42.4
autofluo AF	183	2.5	1.1
GFP total	0	0.0	0.0
negative	7,058	97.4	41.3
GFP strong	0	0.0	0.0
GFP weak	0	0.0	0.0
PI+	1,608	17.8	9.4
viable PI-	9,561	56.0	56.0
P1	6,801	39.8	39.8